

SOCIAL JUSTICE AS A SPECIFIC PRINCIPLE OF GOVERNANCE

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INTRODUCTION

We can say that justice is both a value and a guiding principle in the regulation and management of social relations in society, in ensuring human freedom and the well-being of society. Social justice, on the other hand, embodies and realizes both value and managerial potential. Otherwise, interest in the functional value of equity in governance is lost. In this sense, the degree of satisfaction of certain interests is the impetus for ensuring social justice. What does it mean. This means that in this case, the concept of justice, which is a part of the spiritual world of human civilization, on the one hand, expresses this interest, and

ABSTRACT

This article discusses a scientific and theoretical analysis of the conceptual aspects of social justice as a governing principle. Historical and philosophical foundations of social justice, as well as the importance of social justice in the formation of the volume and content of the general social space of social aspirations in society, the formation of certain directions of people's ideas about freedom and well-being.

on the other, creates an opportunity to satisfy it. Moreover, its first side is assessed morally, and the second - politically. This, in turn, provides a wide opportunity for the formation of interests as an instrument of transition from the unknown side to the unknown in the study of the socio-political life of society, as well as the development of the ability to satisfy it. In this sense, it is in modern society that it provides the basis for predicting to what extent the socio-political function of social justice is reflected.

The value-functional approach to justice in socio-political life, especially in social management, allows one to evaluate and

study its significant potential as a value in a specific environment in which justice exists and is practiced. By its functional nature, justice has a changing nature in time and space in terms of its essence and possibility. These are assessed by the constant changes in social values and the current state of the level of stability. It is these spiritual-moral, legal, political and other values that determine the place and role of justice in the mechanism of social governance at certain moments and intervals. For this reason, Alisher Navoi, in his book *Mahbub-ul Qulub*, likens the righteous king to the light of the morning, and the tyrant to the night covered with a veil of darkness.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

All values are the product of the historical, social and cultural development of society. In any society, justice does not reflect the uniqueness of existing life forms, but their viability in a changing world. This idea can be illustrated with the following example. In the development of Uzbekistan during the Soviet era, a certain system of values was formed in society. They are reflected in socialist values. The past decades of drastic reforms have led to great losses, primarily in the spiritual sphere of public life. The collapse of the social structure and the system of political governance of society, the redistribution of property and many other events had a negative impact on the processes associated with the implementation of justice, the formation of new social perceptions of its image. However, it can be assumed that such a trend in social consciousness may change in the near future. After all, in the next period of the so-called New Uzbekistan, when the mass

psychology and public consciousness of the population is changing, this trend still allows many researchers to form a clear and understandable picture of a just society. In such a situation, justice as a functional value for society is first and foremost a value as a concretely realized idea with many manifestations. This idea lives in the minds of its owners and in the instructions they create, allowing them to develop a new strategy of social relations in a clearly existing functional system of distribution, gift, or exchange relations. For example, in terms of coordinating the desires and needs of society, "all governments will have to adapt the requirements of their citizens to their disabilities in order to satisfy them" [2]. Sociological surveys conducted over the past few years show that more than half of the respondents believe that their dreams will come true rather than not. Therefore, it can be assumed that social justice is perceived by society as an end, means and result of the implementation of the mechanism of social management. At the same time, social justice as an important aspect of this social system of a special quality acts as a guiding principle for the development of the social system.

Justice determines the scale and content of the common social space of social aspirations in society, specific areas of people's perception of freedom and well-being. It is this idea of social justice that manifests itself as the goal of society, to be more precise, as part of a higher order. For this reason, A.Sh. Kholbekov and T.B. Matibaev in their monograph "Social justice and democracy: on the path to sustainable development" listed 14 specific rules of justice [3]. These rules are cited as a

condition for the existence of justice as a social phenomenon. In our view, it is necessary to specify the functional features of these rules. For example, there is ambiguity in the analysis of the “rule of supply and demand”. Because if we look at supply and demand as a relatively independent social phenomenon, we inevitably see that there are contradictions between them. With the priority of one side or the other, the principles of justice are violated. This is also acknowledged by the authors themselves. That is, “Absolutely just society, that is, society itself does not exist and will not exist.” [4]

Justice as an example of high-level human aspirations is also shaped within the framework of certain political and legal perspectives that prevail and are implemented in a certain socio-cultural environment. Currently, there is a gradual integration of conceptual approaches to the interpretation of events and processes of social life. A society that develops in accordance with its objective laws, and the knowledge available in it by the 21st century, is not at all sufficient to study the practical values of society and its management capabilities. A complex system of interdependencies in the unstable development of the social world in the 21st century, socio-economic chaos, revolutionary changes in science and technology are currently explained by the transition from traditional to postmodernism in the axiological study of social phenomena. For example, in the context of the paradigms of the theory of cognitive development proposed by Kolberg [5] and his followers, the study of justice, the theory of justice, theories of objectivity and procedural justice is

becoming increasingly relevant [6]. We are talking here about the results of a complete generalization of objective and subjective knowledge of nature, society and man, which manifests itself as social justice, which emerges as a valuable functional principle of sustainable provision of social justice, preservation and creation of real and virtual life. Such considerations need a certain scientific and philosophical basis, especially political. If such grounds do not exist, they can be taken as assumptions.

Social justice as a political goal in social management is characterized by many signs of its manifestation in the value-functional criterion. These symptoms include: firstly, justice is a key feature of the goals of a country’s national strategy for sustainable development, and secondly, justice exists as a rapidly evolving abstract-concrete idea that must always conform to the existing system of values in the socio-political environment, thirdly, it is known in a hidden invisible state, but in any case must conform to the parameters of measurement, in this sense, it is the result of personal and social experience, universal philosophical and political thinking and the creation of certain civilization (western or eastern) values; the process is internally contradictory and ambiguous because it is influenced by many subjective and objective factors; fifth, it is determined by the interests of its owners and is always a cumulative expression of the purpose of the aspirations of the majority or the minority.

Social justice as an abstract concrete idea is the goal of society’s aspirations, unites complex social processes and acts in traditional societies not only as a connecting basis for survival, but also for

development. The historical power of the ideas of social justice is ensured by the stability and succession of the value system of society, its coexistence with the ideas of freedom and equality, and its timely and effective response to changes in social relations in the mechanism of social governance.

The issue of social justice in governance does not disappear even as the achievement of justice for many representatives of civilization becomes their task in the fight against injustice, inequality and arbitrariness. Therefore, in order not to violate the standards of justice in society, in any state "... as long as the king's activities are based on the laws of justice, he considers every category of people equal before the law, prohibits oppression and cruelty and excessive demands"[7]. Justice as a result of the functioning of a social governance mechanism is some intermediate result of the achievement of something relevant, i.e., an ideological pattern of distribution, gift or exchange, or a product of social justice that reflects a different system of relations. In this sense, moving in a certain direction in a rapidly changing social relationship is more important than achieving the desired. Assessment of justice as a result of the action of the mechanism of social control always takes into account the specifics of the historical period as part of the general historical process.

Social justice as a means of the mechanism of social control is explained by its instrumental capabilities, which are reflected in certain forms of functional orientation. Such forms of social justice can include forms of administration of justice, which differ from each other in the

instrumental application to achieve specific goals, as well as in the forms of its occurrence. For example, we are talking about the specific possibilities of the instrumental use of justice in the creation of a common space of communication in which the right to participate in the competition belongs to a person belonging to different cultures, a social group. In this case, the main question that needs to be answered in order to create a mechanism of social governance is how to ensure the achievement of the ideal of human civilization (western and eastern) justice? will have to find an answer to the question. For example, Munis Khorezmi says about justice: "Only in countries where justice is celebrated can there be trust, respect and harmony between the ruler and the people"[8]. Therefore, the problem of developing various socio-political criteria for ensuring justice is of particular importance. It is about adapting this tool of social management to modern conditions of social development. These functional criteria must be coordinated, synchronous, and the effect of their movements in space and time must be unified. In doing so, they must ensure that the capabilities of the instrument under consideration are identified and implemented that will be effective in achieving the ideals of a just society. As noted above, justice is also characterized by the ability to choose one form or another of it as a tool and ensure the achievement of the goals of its mechanism of social management. In this regard, as one of the important criteria for the full provision of social justice in management, it is necessary to create in practice a wide range of opportunities to perform the functional function of justice.

It is in the implementation of social justice that justice serves to ensure consistency in the achievement of one or another goal of social governance in the common space of life forms.

CONCLUSION

In short, social justice as a special management principle is the manifestation of the results of applying various criteria, methods and tools in the process of managing justice. Moreover, the beginning of their relevance to society in practice is determined by the degree of dissatisfaction of those who are able to apply, implement

and adapt justice to the current state of social justice as a moral and ethical criterion. It should also be noted that justice is viewed as a complex problem of the transition of social management from a state of opportunity to reality in modern society. The reason for this can be explained, first of all, by the fact that ideas about the political situation and the relationship of social justice are determined in the minds of those who today are able to clearly change the situation.

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